

PROGNOSTIC FACTORS RELATED TO THE CLINICAL COURSE AND SEVERITY OF PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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To identify prognostic factors associated with the clinical course and severity of pneumonia in children and assess their impact on the outcome of the disease

ABSTRACT

Pneumonia is the most common respiratory disease among children and is one of the leading causes of death and complications. The severity and clinical course of the disease depend on the age of the child, the immune status, the presence of chronic diseases and the etiology of the infection. Identification of prognostic factors is important for early assessment of the course of pneumonia, timely and effective treatment planning, as well as for reducing the duration of hospital stay and the risk of severe complications.

Introduction. Pneumonia is the most common respiratory disease among children and is one of the leading causes of death and complications. The severity and clinical course of the disease depend on the age of the child, the immune status, the presence of chronic diseases and the etiology of the infection. Identification of prognostic factors is important for early assessment of the course of pneumonia, timely and effective treatment planning, as well as for reducing the duration of hospital stay and the risk of severe complications.

Objective. To identify prognostic factors associated with the clinical course and severity of pneumonia in children and assess their impact on the outcome of the disease.

Materials and methods. The study involved 120 children aged 1–12 years, who were hospitalized with pneumonia. Clinical examination: temperature, respiratory rate, cough, sputum condition, assessment of shift signs. Laboratory tests: hemogram, CRP (C-reactive protein), ESR (erythrocyte sedimentation rate), sputum microscopy and bacteriological examination. Radiological examination: chest X-ray. Severity of the disease was assessed as mild, moderate and severe. Statistical analysis: SPSS software, $p < 0.05$ significant.

Results. Clinical course: Mild pneumonia: 50% of children, mainly with fever and cough. Moderate severity: 35%, increased respiratory rate, abundant sputum. Severe pneumonia: 15%, high temperature, respiratory failure, generalized infection. Prognostic factors: Age < 2 years: high risk of severe pneumonia ($r = 0.52$; $p < 0.01$). The presence of chronic disease (bronchitis, cardiovascular disease) increases the severity. Reduced immunity (low IgG and IgA) is associated with a severe clinical course. Etiology: bacterial infection is more associated with a severe course, viral pneumonia is often mild. Duration of hospitalization: Mild pneumonia: average 5 ± 1.2 days. Average severity: 8 ± 2.1 days. Severe pneumonia: 12 ± 3.5 days

Conclusion. The clinical course of pneumonia in children depends on age, chronic diseases, immune status, and etiology. Children <2 years of age and those with chronic diseases are at high risk of developing severe pneumonia. Identification of prognostic factors is important for timely and effective treatment of the disease, reducing complications, and shortening the duration of hospitalization. In pediatric practice, an individualized treatment regimen and monitoring help prevent the development of severe pneumonia.

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